

Sustainability in Foodpanda: A correlational study of small and medium-sized enterprises and consumers in Bacoor City

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the level of sustainability in using Foodpanda in ordering food for small and medium-sized enterprises to know if Foodpanda promotes sustainability. It took place in the City of Bacoor, a first-class city in the province of Cavite, Philippines. The samples were chosen through purposive sampling because of the COVID-19 pandemic when the research was made and gathered around 50 small business owners and 50 consumers. Foodpanda is considered sustainable by the consumer group because it reduces meal preparation time as well as the cost of power and gas. Foodpanda also encourages families to eat together and converse more while they wait for their food to be delivered. The sustainability of Foodpanda is questioned by small food entrepreneurs. They observed that the internet delivery platform does not promote small food enterprises. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the sustainability of using the online food delivery platform, Foodpanda, based on the findings.

Keywords: *Foodpanda; Online food delivery systems; Sustainability.*

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Introduction

Economic growth and increasing reliance on the internet are driving the global expansion of e-commerce (Ahmed & Ahmed, 2016). Consumers are increasingly using online services as their expendable income increases, electronic payments become more reliable, and the range of suppliers and the size of their delivery networks expand, especially in the food delivery business (Saakyan & Shpekht, 2019). Online to offline is a form of online commerce in which consumers are attracted to a product or service online and instigated to complete a transaction in an offline setting, with examples such as Lazada, Zalora, Foodpanda, GrabFood, and Shopee. An area of this type of commerce that is expanding rapidly is the use of online food delivery system platforms. All around the world, the rise of online food delivery systems has changed the way that many consumers and food suppliers interact and the sustainability impacts, which are defined by the three pillars of economic, social, and environmental. Part of the difficulty in assessing its impact has been that researchers are approaching this topic from a range of various disciplines. Thus, the objectives of this review are twofold, which is to discuss the opportunities and challenges these impacts pose and to highlight the opportunities for action by all stakeholders, including online food industry practitioners, policymakers, consumers, and academics, to maximize its positive and reduce its adverse impacts.

The utilization of information and communication technologies, simply known as ICT, can be regarded as one of the innovative ways to help small food outlets improve their business performance in the competitive market. The business activities of a company that is virtually using ICT are known as e-commerce, or in common terms, online business (Guo et al., 2012). E-commerce in the food industry has penetrated the application of smartphones with ICT such as Foodpanda, which has brought great impact for not only restaurants and fast-food franchises but as well as small food outlets.

Over the last decade, there has been a noticeable shift in customers' preference toward online purchases and information gathering because platforms and applications allow people to shop in the comfort of their own homes and at their own leisure and time without the hassle of leaving home (Jiang et al., 2013). Moreover, in a context where businesses are pressured to make hard decisions with restricted information (Ayithey et al., 2020), online shopping seems to have expanded. The convenience of online purchases, in terms of overall evaluations and transactions, has been depicted to enhance customer satisfaction and encourage positive reviews and recommendations through social media such as Facebook and Twitter (Duarte et al., 2018). This is also why most small food outlets have responded to such preferences by increasingly adopting new platforms and digital applications with the aim of improving customers' experience and promotion, therefore competing with fast-food franchises and restaurants (Reinartz et al., 2019).

In ICT, social presence, perceived enjoyment, and trust have been carefully recorded to assess the intentions behind technology use (Chemingui & Iallouna, 2013 as cited by De Cicco et al., 2021). According to empirical studies, it shows that perceived social presence positively influences both enjoyment and trust of consumers (Cyr et al., 2007). As a matter of fact, consumers experience a higher degree of social presence, in which they are more probable to escape from the real world and enter an arousing, pleasurable mental state, such as enjoyment and bliss (Gao et al., 2017). Comparably, social presence instigates more transparency in a less trustworthy environment (Lu et al., 2016) by reducing the perceived social distance between buyers and sellers. Various research studies that focus on the online environment confirm the positive effect of social presence on trust and perceived enjoyment in contexts such as social media sites and online stores (Ogonowski et al., 2014).

Small food outlets have been shown to have boosted sales because of the implications of online food delivery services in countries such as Thailand (Duangkanya, 2018), Vietnam (Du et al., 2019), Russia (Frangyan, 2020), Armenia (Javatov & Khalitova, 2020), and many more. Another implication that boosted the promulgation of small food outlets is the closure of food premises and the lack of food services in shops or restaurants due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which caused some people to lose their source of income due to the inability of employers to cover the cost of workers' salaries and in turn started online forms of businesses (Che Suhaili et al., 2020).

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the level of sustainability of Foodpanda on small and medium-sized enterprises and consumers in Bacoor City. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the online food business in terms of:
 - 1.1 Size of enterprise;
 - 1.2 Type of cuisine served;
 - 1.3 Classification (restaurant/take-out store/home-based kitchen);
 - 1.4 Length of operation; and,
 - 1.5 Range of income/profit?
2. What is the demographic profile of the consumers?

- 2.1 Number of family members in the household;
 - 2.2 Range of income; and,
 - 2.3 Occupational status?
3. What is the level of sustainability of Foodpanda on small and medium food businesses in terms of:
 - 3.1 Economical;
 - 3.2 Social; and,
 - 3.3 Environmental?

Hypothesis

The null hypotheses that were tested in this study are as follows:

Ho1: Foodpanda has no significant level of economical sustainability in Bacoor City.

Ho2: Foodpanda has no significant level of social sustainability in Bacoor City.

Ho3: Foodpanda has no significant level of environmental sustainability in Bacoor City.

Ho4: Foodpanda is not a sustainable online food delivery service in Bacoor City.

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the researchers used a quantitative research approach. This study examines the relationship between variables and the levels of sustainability of Foodpanda on Bacoor City small food outlets and consumers. This study was accomplished through a survey sample questionnaire, consisting of two (2) parts—one for the demographic questions and the other is a Likert scale for the rating of the level of sustainability of Foodpanda on small and medium-sized food outlets. Questionnaires were completed and provided by the researchers. There are two (2) sets of questionnaires, and they are different for the business owners and the consumers but follow the same format.

Locale of the Study

The research locale is limited to the City of Bacoor in the province of Cavite. The respondents were asked to answer using online forms as given by the researchers with the use of Google Forms. Due to the circumstances of the current situation when the research is written, the survey cannot be disseminated in person; thus, the researchers took advantage of the use of an online form.

Respondents of the Study

The samples were chosen through purposive sampling because of the COVID-19 pandemic when the research was made. The target is to gather around 50 small business owners and 50 consumers in Bacoor City, Cavite, for the sample of the study.

Sample Size

According to Cristobal (2013), stratified sampling is a method of sampling from a population that can be partitioned into subpopulations. Stratified sampling ensures each subgroup within the population can receive proper representation within a sample. In turn, stratified random sampling provides better coverage of the population since the authors have more control over the subgroups to ensure that all of them are represented in the sampling. The researchers categorized the respondents into barangay divisions of Bacoor City, which are divided into two: Bacoor West (District 1) and Bacoor 2 (District 2).

Research Instrumentation

There are two instruments to be used in this study, which are both quantitative tests. These tests are only self-made questionnaires and are divided based on respondent groups, which are business owners and consumers. The quantitative test identifies the location of the respondent in barangay divisions as well as the theme of the food that they served. A Likert scale is used to rate the levels of sustainability in Foodpanda of small and medium-sized food outlets and consumers.

Data Collection

Respondents are small food outlet owners in Bacoor City partnered with Foodpanda for food deliveries. They are all residents of Bacoor, and the food outlet is located within one of the barangays of Bacoor City. The participants are willing to participate in the said research study. The researchers disseminated the survey with Google survey forms.

Data Analysis Procedure

The researchers tried to assess the levels of sustainability in Foodpanda of small food outlets and consumers in Bacoor City, which is based upon the perceptions of the food outlet owners and consumers, to create a basis for a program to enhance the sustainability of local food outlets. The researchers of the study followed the specified procedures below to conduct the study:

1. The researchers prepared a self-made questionnaire to identify the level of sustainability in Foodpanda for small and medium-sized enterprises and consumers in Bacoor City.
2. The researchers disseminated the questionnaires to the appropriate participants of the study to gather the necessary data.
3. Finally, the researchers tried to analyze the gathered data from the corresponding questionnaires to create a basis for a counseling procedure.

Ethical Considerations

The following ethical guidelines were put into place for the study period:

1. The dignity and well-being of the students were always guarded.
2. The research data remained confidential throughout the study, and the researcher obtained consent to use their personal information in the research.

The researchers continued to always be objective during the research period, and no attempt was made to persuade the students to adopt viewpoints that were different from those they held. In terms of the analysis and interpretation of the questionnaires and examination results, the collected data was quantifiable and could be interpreted in an objective manner by means of statistical analysis. The journals and oral interviews nonetheless required a more inferential method and one in which the researcher’s interpretive ability and judgment came into play. Precise procedures were put into place to ensure that the patterns and themes in the data were defined.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1 shows that most of the customers in Bacoor City have four or five people in their household, which represents 54 percent of the total sample, sharing 27 percent. Half of the sample is shared between three members per household (18%) and followed by six members per household (14%).

Figure 1. Percent distribution of customers by number of people in household

Figure 2 highlights that most customers prefer local Filipino cuisines in Bacoor City. It is also notable that in sweets and desserts, milk tea was ordered by thirty of the fifty customers in the study. Western foods from pasta, pizza, and other fast-food items are also highly preferred by half of the customers.

Figure 2. Graph distribution of customers by the type of cuisines in the past month

Meanwhile, Figure 3 shows that half (52%) of the customers of Foodpanda earn below ₱10,000, which revolves around the minimum salary of the Philippines as of 2021, which is ₱7,385. It is followed by people who earn between ₱10,000-₱25,000, which compromises 22%; then, it is enduringly followed by people who earn between the range of ₱25,000-₱50,000, in which it contains 18% of the sample; and finally, by people who earn more than ₱50,000 that makes up the final eight percent of the data.

Figure 3. Percent distribution of customers by range of income

Figure 4 shows that most of the local food businesses in Bacoor are small businesses owned by a single owner, which consists of 39 of the 50 business enterprises sampled, or 78 percent of the total sample percentage. It is followed by family-owned small businesses with less than 10 employees and small business enterprises with more than 11 employees, which both represent 8 percent each of the sample data. There is a 6% for the small family business with more than 11 employees, and there are no medium-size business enterprises in Bacoor City gathered as there are none such exist.

Figure 4. Percent distribution of local food businesses by size of business

Most of the food businesses in the City of Bacoor sell milk tea, which makes up 37 percent of the total sample (Figure 5), where it comprises more than a third of the 50 gathered samples for food businesses. It is then followed by fast food and chicken wing restaurants with eighteen percent.

Figure 6 shows that 24 food businesses earn below ₱10,000 per month, which makes up 47% of the total sample. 33% of the data earns between the range of ₱10,000-₱25,000, which is followed by businesses that earn between ₱25,000-₱50,000, which represents twelve percent of the data. There are only four food establishments that earn more than ₱50,000 per month.

Figure 5. Percent distribution of local food businesses by the type of cuisines they cater

Figure 6. Percent distribution of businesses by range of income

Table 1 shows the frequency distribution of the customers in the study, in which it depicts that most of the customers in Bacoor city that uses Foodpanda are mostly around four to five per household and have an income of below ₱10,000 per month.

Table 1. Frequency Distribution Per Demographic Profile of Customers (n=50)

Demographic Profile	Indicators	Frequency	Percentage	Rank	
Number of People in Household	2	3	6	5	
	3	9	18	3	
	4	13	26	1.5	
	5	13	26	1.5	
	6	7	14	4	
	7	1	2	7.3	
	8	2	4	6	
	10	1	2	7.3	
	11	1	2	7.3	
	Range of Income	Below ₱10,000	26	52	1
		₱10,000-₱25,000	11	22	2
₱25,000-₱50,000		9	18	3	
More than ₱25,000		4	8	4	

Most of the food ordered by the participants of the study in a single month was mostly Filipino food (Table 2), followed by milk tea, fast food items, and chicken wings. There is a chance that participants will order local cuisine 19% of the time in a single month every time they use Foodpanda as their delivery provider. There is also a significant percent distribution for milk tea, fast food, and pizza, with 15%, 14%, and 12% distribution, respectively. Seventy percent of the total sample had bought local Filipino food in a single month. Bread and pastries and Chinese cuisines were the least preferred cuisines by the participants of the study. Meanwhile, fast food items and chicken wings had an equal preference from the respondents.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Type of Cuisines Ordered by Customers in a Month (n=50)

Type of Cuisine	Frequency	Percent Distribution	Percent of Cases
Local Filipino Cuisine	35	19	70
Japanese Cuisine	11	6	22
Korean Cuisine	13	7	26
Chinese Cuisine	10	5	20
Western Cuisine (Pasta)	17	9	34
Western Cuisine (Pizza)	23	12	46
Western Cuisine (Fast-food and Chicken Wings)	25	14	50
Cafe	14	8	28
Milk Tea (Bubble Tea)	30	15	60
Bread and Pastries	10	5	20
Total	188	100	

Table 3 shows that most of the food business enterprises in Bacoor City are small personal businesses, milk tea shops, and have a range of income of below ten thousand pesos.

Table 3. Frequency Distribution Per Demographic Profile of Online Food Business Owners (n=50)

Demographic Profile	Indicators	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Size of Business	Small Personal Business (1-10)	39	78	1
	Small Family Business (1-10)	4	8	2.5
	Small Family Business (11-50)	3	6	4
	Small Business (11-50)	4	8	2.5
Type of Food Business	Local Filipino Cuisine	5	10	3.3
	Japanese Cuisine	4	8	6
	Korean Cuisine	5	10	3.3
	Chinese Cuisine	1	2	9.5
	Western Cuisine (Pasta)	2	4	7.5
	Western Cuisine (Pizza)	2	4	7.5
	Western Cuisine (Fast Food and Chicken Wings)	10	20	2
	Cafe	5	10	3.3
	Milk Tea (Bubble Tea)	21	42	1
Bread and Pastries	1	2	9.5	
Range of Income	Below ₱10,000	24	48	1
	₱10,000-₱25,000	17	34	2
	₱25,000-₱50,000	6	12	3
	More than ₱25,000	4	8	4

Based on the inferences from Table 4, the mean average for the responses of the customers is 3.75, which means that most customers, across various demographic profiles, all agreed that Foodpanda is sustainable to a certain degree. Customers with large households are divided between Foodpanda being exceedingly sustainable and improvident or wasteful.

Table 4. Mean Scores of Customers for Foodpanda Sustainability Level

Demographic Profile	Indicators	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Description
Number of People in Household	2	3.33	Neutral	Neither sustainable nor improvident
	3	3.71	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	4	4.19	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	5	3.53	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	6	3.76	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	7	5.00	Strongly Agree	Exceedingly sustainable
	8	2.53	Somewhat Disagree	Improvident
	10	4.47	Strongly Agree	Sustainable
	11	3.07	Neutral	Neither sustainable nor improvident
Type of Cuisine	Local Filipino Cuisine	3.87	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Japanese Cuisine	3.96	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Korean Cuisine	4.10	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Chinese Cuisine	4.14	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Western Cuisine (Pasta)	3.92	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Western Cuisine (Pizza)	3.94	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Western Cuisine (Fast Food and Chicken Wings)	3.87	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Cafe	4.04	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Milk Tea (Bubble Tea)	4.00	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Bread and Pastries	4.18	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
Range of Income	Below ₱10,000	3.79	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	₱10,000-₱25,000	3.69	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	₱25,000-₱50,000	3.61	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	More than ₱25,000	4.17	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
Total Average		3.75	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable

Table 5 shows that most of the small businesses in Bacoor City disagree that Foodpanda is sustainable and does not promote their businesses through Foodpanda advertising. The range of income per month affects how the small business owners see the sustainability of Foodpanda, as most businesses who earn more than twenty-five thousand pesos per month agree that Foodpanda is more sustainable for them than people who earn below twenty-five thousand pesos. The type of cuisine has a mixed response to the sustainability of Foodpanda, as people see Western cuisines and fast-food items as sustainable, but others disagree that bread and pastries, milk tea, and Chinese and Filipino foods in Foodpanda are sustainable and improvident.

In Table 6, the p-value of the t-test is 0.000223, which is less than the alpha value of 0.05; therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the two groups, which are the customers and the small- and medium-sized establishments.

Based on the results of the study, there is a significant difference in the sustainability of using the online food delivery platform, Foodpanda, based on the opinions of most of our participants, who are consumers and food industry managers. Most consumers, regardless of demographic profile, agree that Foodpanda is sustainable to some extent. Customers with large homes are split between Foodpanda being extremely sustainable to a degree and being imprudent or wasteful. Meanwhile, local companies in Bacoor City disagree that Foodpanda is sustainable and that Foodpanda advertising does not assist in advertising their products.

Table 5. Mean Scores of Online Food Business Owners for Foodpanda Sustainability Level

Demographic Profile	Indicators	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Description
Size of Business	Small Personal Business (1-10)	2.94	Neutral	Neither sustainable nor improvident
	Small Family Business (1-10)	2.47	Somewhat Disagree	Improvident
	Small Family Business (11-50)	1.27	Strongly Disagree	Exceedingly improvident
	Small Business (11-50)	2.53	Somewhat Disagree	Improvident
Type of Food Business	Local Filipino Cuisine	2.18	Somewhat Disagree	Improvident
	Japanese Cuisine	3.20	Neutral	Neither sustainable nor improvident
	Korean Cuisine	3.73	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Chinese Cuisine	2.18	Somewhat Disagree	Improvident
	Western Cuisine (Pasta)	3.73	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Western Cuisine (Pizza)	3.81	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Western Cuisine (Fast Food and Chicken Wings)	4.20	Strongly Agree	Exceedingly sustainable
	Cafe	3.97	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	Milk Tea (Bubble Tea)	2.82	Somewhat Disagree	Improvident
Bread and Pastries	1.27	Strongly Disagree	Exceedingly improvident	
Range of Income	Below ₱10,000	2.38	Somewhat Disagree	Improvident
	₱10,000-₱25,000	2.84	Neutral	Neither sustainable nor improvident
	₱25,000-₱50,000	4.10	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
	More than ₱25,000	3.73	Somewhat Agree	Sustainable
Total Average		2.85	Neutral	Neither sustainable nor improvident

Table 6. T-Test: Paired Two Samples for Mean

	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	4.034667	2.773333
Variance	0.676341	1.475556
Observations	25	25
Pearson Correlation	0.019316	
Difference	0	
df	24	
t Stat	4.338293	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.000112	
t Critical one-tail	1.710882	

The range of monthly income affects how small business owners view Foodpanda's sustainability, as most firms earning more than 25 thousand pesos per month think that Foodpanda is more sustainable for them than people earning less than 25 thousand pesos. The type of cuisine has a mixed reaction to Foodpanda's sustainability; users see Western cuisines and quick food consider its sustainability in Foodpanda, whereas bread and pastries, milk tea, Chinese food, and Filipino food were disagreed by other people.

There is a big disparity between the two groups: customers and small and medium-sized businesses. It suggests that there are significant differences in the outcomes of the two groups, namely consumers and small enterprises. As the inferences reveal, consumers assume that the online delivery platform Foodpanda is viable, whereas local small businesses believe the reverse.

Conclusion

As a result, the study concludes and addresses the study's problem statements. This study includes 100 Bacoor City residents divided into two groups. Each group has 50 samples, divided into two groups: customers and owners and managers of small food businesses. The majority of Bacoor's local food businesses are small firms operated by a single person, accounting for 39 commercial enterprises, or 78 percent of the overall sample percentage. It is followed by family-owned small firms with fewer than ten employees and small commercial enterprises with more than eleven employees, which each account for 8% of the sample data. There is a 6% representation for small family businesses with more than 11 employees, and there are no medium-sized company firms assembled in Bacoor City because none exist. Most of the food businesses in the City of Bacoor are milk tea shops, accounting for 37% of the overall sample and accounting for more than a third of the 50 acquired samples for food businesses. It is followed by fast food and chicken wing restaurants, which account for 18% of the market. Twenty-four food enterprises make less than ₱10,000 each month, accounting for 47 percent of the whole sample. Firms earning between ₱10,000 and ₱25,000 account for 33% of the data, followed by businesses earning between ₱25,000 and ₱50,000, accounting for 12% of the data. Only four culinary enterprises earn more than ₱50,000 per month.

The study includes 38 people who have fewer than five members in their family and 12 people who have more than six people in their family. The study included 26 clients with less than ₱10,000 in income and 24 respondents with more than ₱10,000 in income. The bulk of customers chose local Filipino food, with over 35 customers in the previous month. Milk tea, fast food, and western cuisine are all popular demands. Meanwhile, in the last few months, customers have ordered coffee, oriental cuisines, and bread and pastries, with less than 11 orders per cuisine.

Foodpanda is seen as sustainable by consumers because it decreases meal preparation time as well as the cost of electricity and gas. It also encourages families to eat together and speak more while waiting for their food. Customers have also mentioned how enticing the reductions and discounts are. The sustainability of Foodpanda is questioned by small food entrepreneurs. They observed that the internet delivery platform does not promote small food enterprises. Most orders come from large fast-food restaurants such as Jollibee and McDonald's. Foodpanda does not also reduce the cost of power and gas. As a result, Foodpanda's sustainability for the two groups differs dramatically. Customers perceive Foodpanda to be sustainable, and small food businesses face an unsustainable market niche.

Recommendations

Online food delivery providers may need to change delivery time regulations with delivery people's advantages and safety in mind to increase economic sustainability by enhancing employee retention. In terms of social sustainability, online food delivery platform providers could contribute to reducing food waste by better communicating with their customers about appropriate portion sizes and without forcing or encouraging them to purchase. In terms of environmental sustainability, the online food delivery industry could consider collaborating with packaging manufacturers as well as the restaurant industry to investigate solutions for the creation and usage of more sustainable packaging materials.

Policymakers should think about how to better regulate food delivery to ensure proper working conditions for delivery workers, which might lead to lower attrition rates and, as a result, enhanced economic viability. To improve social sustainability, policymakers should use education to enhance public knowledge of sustainability and good eating habits. More importantly, they might improve applicable legislation and regulations to explain the rights and obligations of each waste management player (e.g., waste management firms, online food delivery companies, and consumers). In terms of environmental sustainability, policymakers should use incentives such as taxation, subsidies, and industrial support to encourage the packaging industry to create innovative packaging materials.

Ordering sensibly and eating healthily would limit the possibility of spending money on food that is not consumed while also avoiding the potential poor health effects associated with overconsumption, giving both economic and health benefits. To improve the social sustainability of online food delivery consumption, users should be encouraged to order and share meals with coworkers or flatmates. Users might separate food and packaging trash after concluding a meal to contribute to environmental sustainability.

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